

Study of some biological effects of humic substances

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Humic substances have been shown to have various biological properties with high therapeutic potential. In this study, humic acids modified with silver nanoparticles (HA-Ag) and fulvic acids (FA) were tested for antibacterial activity, cytotoxicity and hemocompatibility.

Humic acids stabilized by silver nanoparticles and fulvic acids were found to have antibacterial activity against the methicillin-resistant strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). The results in the table 1 show the antimicrobial activity of HA-Ag and FA.

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of HA-Ag and FA. Green indicates complete suppression of bacterial growth, and red indicates the absence of it

HA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200		FA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200
Ag, µg ml ⁻¹	0	4.7	14.7	22.0	29.4	36.7	73.5									

The presence of FA in the nutrient media did not have a significant toxic effect on DF cultured in them for 2 days: cell viability was comparable to the control or close to it. The content of HA-Ag in the nutrient medium in all studied concentrations had a weakly expressed cytotoxic effect on DF cultured in them for 2 days: cell viability was lower than the control, but higher than 80%.

An assessment of the hemocompatibility of FA and HA-Ag was carried out. It was established that FA do not have hemolytic activity. HA-Ag with concentrations below 40 mg/L do not have hemolytic activity. Concentrations from 60 to 100 mg/L have a weak hemolytic activity. Concentration 200 mg/L has a high hemolytic activity (table 2).

Table 2. Hemolytic activity of HA-Ag and FA. Green indicates the absence of hemolytic activity, yellow indicates weak hemolytic activity, and red indicates high hemolytic activity

HA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200		FA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200
Ag, µg ml ⁻¹	0	7.4	14.7	22.0	29.4	36.7	73.5									

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